

Demand for Inclusive Products for Individuals With Additional Educational Requirements

Kurbanova Munavvara Abdujabbarovna

Professor at the Alisher Navoi Tashkent State University of the Uzbek Language and Literature, Doctor of Philological Sciences (DSc)

Article information:

Manuscript received: 11 Oct 2024; **Accepted:** 12 Nov 2024; **Published:** 12 Dec 2024

Annotation: The article presents a discussion of the provision of inclusive products designed for students with additional educational needs, including students and researchers. It provides information about audiobooks and special computer programs that have been integrated into the inclusive education system in Uzbekistan. Furthermore, the practical implications of the findings from the laboratory, which was established with the objective of developing inclusive educational and scientific products, are discussed.

Keywords: inclusive product, inclusive education, individual with disabilities, audiobook, speech synthesiser, information resource, speech corpus, speech recognition software.

Introduction

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the creation of comprehensive and accessible conditions for inclusive education for students with additional educational needs has become a priority within the national policy agenda. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1], the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" [2], and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. On 13 October 2020, Mirziyoyev signed the decree "On measures to further improve the education system for children with special educational needs" PQ-4860-son [3], which outlines the tasks for creating equal opportunities for inclusive education for students with disabilities. The Concept for the Development of Inclusive Education in the Public Education System for 2020-2025 [4] also addresses this issue, with particular attention paid to the provision of inclusive products.

At the present time, particular initiatives are being implemented in Uzbekistan with the objective of furnishing students and researchers with disabilities with the necessary information resources. To illustrate, the practical grant project A-1-61, entitled "Creating Audiobook Provisions for Students with Limited Vision in Linguistics," which was conducted under the auspices of the state scientific and technical programs from 2015 to 2017, resulted in the production of 14 audiobooks. The project resulted in the production of textbooks, study guides, course works, and master's thesis writing guides in various fields, including "History of the Uzbek Language," "Theory of Linguistics," "Modern Uzbek Literary Language," "Sociolinguistics," and "Psycholinguistics." Additionally, audiobook versions of these materials were created, along with monographs, dissertations, and collections of audio information reflecting the content of scientific articles published in prestigious journals. The aforementioned resources were made available to information-resource centres throughout Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan, showcased on the Ziyonet educational portal, and incorporated into the Moodle and Hemis e-learning platforms. They were also made available to the public via the Telegram channel

https://t.me/filologiya_mediya_manbalar.

Between 2018 and 2020, the "UzNutq Sintezator" computer program, which converts text into spoken voice through speech synthesis, was developed at the Alisher Navoi Tashkent State University of the Uzbek Language and Literature with the objective of expanding the ability of visually impaired students and researchers to utilise educational and scientific literature in Uzbek, and to work independently with Uzbek-language electronic texts. The program was developed as part of a wider initiative to integrate these students into the inclusive education system. The initial version of this Uzbek speech synthesiser was developed under the auspices of the state practical grant BV-Atex-2018 (143), entitled "Developing speaking software and voice synthesiser based on the Uzbek language for visually impaired persons to use computers, read and write texts". This speech synthesiser, the inaugural product of its kind in Uzbekistan based on artificial intelligence technology, was launched online via the "@ttsuzbot" Telegram bot and popularised through the website <http://uznutq.com/>. The program is capable of vocalizing texts recorded in both Cyrillic and Latin Uzbek alphabets in accordance with the standards of literary pronunciation. In 2023, the linguistic and audio information database was also effectively employed in the development of an Uzbek speech synthesiser based on RH Voice technology, initiated by the Tashkent City Centre for Visually Impaired Youth.

Main part

The rapid advancement of science and technology requires the continuous updating of educational and scientific literature and the optimisation of specialised software products for the inclusive education system. In this regard, the establishment of a research laboratory dedicated to the creation of accessible and user-friendly tools and media products for inclusive education is of paramount importance. In light of the aforementioned considerations, the "Inclusive Education" scientific-practical laboratory was inaugurated on 19 December 2023 at the Tashkent State University of the Uzbek Language and Literature. The laboratory's activities occupy a distinctive position in terms of their systematic application of scientific and creative approaches and analysis methods related to inclusive education resources. They also extend research in this area through innovative technologies and coordinate them.

The objective of the laboratory is to facilitate the independent utilisation of educational and scientific literature, as well as modern information tools, by students with additional educational needs by developing a comprehensive range of inclusive products.

The laboratory's responsibilities encompass the following:

- the objective is to examine the prerequisites for information sources and tools in the inclusive education system that are essential and accessible for continuous use by students with additional educational needs;
- the adoption and creative utilisation of global best practices in the creation of inclusive products based on innovative approaches, technologies and modern research methods;
- the objective is to define the research directions for the laboratory and to develop a roadmap for activities that is aligned with these directions;
- the composition of the laboratory workforce, along with the scientific, methodological and material-technical bases that underpin it, must be considered;
- the objective is to expand the database of products designed for the inclusive education system. In addition, projects related to the creation of educational and scientific literature and special computer programs are to be prepared, implemented, and collaborations with experienced specialists in the republic and abroad established;
- the dissemination of analytical data regarding the activities of the laboratory to the general public, the testing of software products in electronic format, and the organisation of websites and Telegram bots for online delivery to users are all key functions of the department;

- the objective is to guarantee the legal protection of the intellectual property generated in the laboratory and to disseminate the findings of the research;
- the results will be implemented in practice through the conclusion of agreements with relevant institutions, namely those engaged in the provision of inclusive education, as well as educational and information resource centres;
- the dissemination of research findings in esteemed scientific journals, both nationally and internationally, participation in presentations at international and national scientific-practical conferences, engagement with print and electronic media, and involvement in exhibitions and scientific competitions held within the context of international and national forums dedicated to innovative ideas in inclusive products are some of the avenues through which the aforementioned objectives are pursued;
- the provision of scientific advice to students and researchers with disabilities, the encouragement of their active participation in reading and other types of competitions, intellectual games, and cultural-educational events alongside their healthy peers, and the dissemination of information about their creative achievements through social networks.

The laboratory's operations are conducted in the following areas:

- the creation of audio content for educational and scientific works across a range of scientific disciplines, with the objective of making it accessible to users via an online platform. The utility of the audio products prepared in the laboratory is largely contingent upon their suitability for utilisation in educational and scientific activities by individuals with visual impairments. Such products include the replication of copies, the dissemination of said copies to users with visual impairments, the augmentation of information resource centres with media resources, and the provision of the ability to listen to books on personal computers, mobile devices, and devices designed for audio playback;
- the provision of educational and scientific literature in Braille to information-resource centres. The provision of literature in Braille is an effective method for enhancing the literacy level of visually impaired students. It allows visually impaired readers to gain a deeper understanding of the spelling of words recorded in embossed-dot writing. This is because the written expression of a word is clearly visible during the reading process, which in turn leads to a stronger retention of the information in long-term memory. In this regard, Braille book products play an important role in developing the linguistic abilities and broadening the worldview of visually impaired students. This, in turn, contributes to their development as morally and spiritually complete individuals, capable of making a worthy contribution to the advancement of science and education;
- the creation of sophisticated computer programs pertaining to speech recognition and their subsequent placement on the Google Play platform. The Uzbek speech synthesiser, which is based on artificial intelligence technology that converts text into spoken messages, provides a convenient interface for visually impaired users to interact with electronic documents. Further developments are conducted in a laboratory setting, whereby the functional capabilities of the software are expanded. This addresses issues related to visually impaired individuals' independent use of electronic educational materials and modern multimedia technologies, as well as their ability to stay informed about news published on internet pages. Those with visual impairments who are highly proficient in computer-related subjects are able to utilise typhlo-technical programmes and devices to perform a range of functions, including listening, reading, writing, editing, calculation, acting as trainers in computer literacy courses and creating basic computer programmes. Such products also play an important role in the development of these individuals as programming specialists.

Those with visual impairments who are proficient in computer skills are able to perform a variety of tasks in different call centres and voice recording studios with the assistance of a speech synthesiser. They are also able to provide rapid practical (software) support to computer users from a distance and to engage in entrepreneurial activities online, thereby transforming into business individuals. Consequently, their

employment is guaranteed.

- the organisation of events within the context of laboratory activities. A series of masterclasses, seminar-trainings and roundtable discussions on issues of inclusive education will be held with the objective of developing new proposals for advancing the laboratory's activities and implementing them in a step-by-step manner.

In order to ensure the effective organisation of laboratory activities, a multidisciplinary team comprising leading scientists from a range of scientific fields, educators, psychologists and defectologists with extensive knowledge and high qualifications in the field of inclusive education, as well as experienced researchers, has been established. The laboratory's scientific-methodological base is constituted by printed and electronic educational guides, methodological instructions, articles, treatises, monographic research, and its material-technical base is organised by computer packages and voice recording equipment adapted for use in the inclusive education process.

Conclusion

In Uzbekistan, there is a notable requirement for products that are accessible to students, learners, and researchers with disabilities. Furthermore, orders can be received from other republics where education is conducted in the Uzbek language. The provision of inclusive products has been demonstrated to enhance self-confidence, intellectual potential, social activity, and the ability to become specialists who meet the contemporary demands of individuals with disabilities. Consequently, the identification of convenient ways to improve the inclusive education system provides opportunities to enhance its quality and effectiveness, as well as to explore ways to extend the continuity and integration of education for individuals with disabilities in society.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi. <https://lex.uz/docs/-6445145>
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasining "Ta'lim to'g'risida"gi Qonuni. <https://lex.uz/docs/-5013007>
3. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. "Alohida ta'lim ehtiyojlari bo'lgan bolalarga ta'lim-tarbiya berish tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PQ-4860-son Qaror. <https://lex.uz/docs/-504471113.10.2020>
4. 2020- 2025-yillarda xalq ta'limi tizimida inklyuziv ta'limni rivojlantirish Konsepsiyasi. <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/5044711#5045924>
5. Qurbonova M., Lutfullayeva D. Va b. Sh.Usmanova muallifligidagi "Psixolingvistika" kursidan ma'ruzalar" qo'llanmasining Audiokitob shaklidagi nusxasi. <https://audio.ziyonet.uz/book/5383>
6. Qurbonova M., Lutfullayeva D. Va b. 2007-2016-yillarda nashr etilgan tilshunoslikka oid monografiyalarning qisqacha mazmuni. Audioma'lumotlar to'plami. <https://audio.ziyonet.uz/book/5394>
7. Qurbonova M., Lutfullayeva D. va b. Filologiya fanlari nomzodi va filologiya fanlari doktori ilmiy darajalarini olish uchun yozilgan tilshunoslikka oid dissertatsiyalarning qisqacha mazmuni (O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining 2007-2016-yillarda nashr etilgan Byulletenlari asosida). Audioma'lumotlar to'plami. <https://audio.ziyonet.uz/book/5394>
8. Qurbonova M., Lutfullayeva D. va b. 2014-2016-yillarda e'lon qilingan tilshunoslik fanlariga oid maqolalarning qisqacha mazmuni ("O'zbek tili va adabiyoti" hamda "Filologiya masalalari") jurnallari asosida. <https://audio.ziyonet.uz/book/5446>